

Viscosity of Ternary Ionic Melts

J. D. PANDEY*, A. K. SHUKLA, (MRS.) SHIKHA and (MISS) N. TRIPATHI

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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Ternary liquid viscosity data have been analysed in the light of the empirical equations by a few workers^{1,2}. But no such attempt has been made for ternary ionic melts. Gaune³ measured viscosity of the $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2\text{-NaNO}_3$ ionic melt at two compositions as a function of temperature. The purpose of the present paper is to apply various empirical relations for computing theoretically the viscosity and related parameters for this ternary ionic melt. A comparative study of the validity of various relations is also made. Further, Flory's statistical theory^{4,5} has been extended for estimating the viscosity in ternary ionic melt. The results obtained are compared with those estimated from the various empirical relations. On the basis of the free volume theory of Macedo and Litovitz⁶ and its improvement over the absolute reaction rate theory of Eyring *et al.*⁷, the Flory theory has been used to predict the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures by Dewan-Bloomfield⁸ and others⁹. The theoretical formalism of these workers has been used recently to study the viscous behaviour of multi-component liquid mixtures. Its has been our aim to utilise their theoretical model for deducing the viscosity and related thermodynamic parameters for binary salt mixtures^{10,11}.

Based on the viscosity data of pure components, a number of equations have been proposed by various workers for the computation of viscosity of mixtures. Considering the ideal mixing of solutions, Bingham¹² proposed the following viscosity equation for ideal binary mixtures : $\eta = x_1\eta_1 + x_2\eta_2$. This has been extended to ternary liquid mixtures,

$$\eta = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i \eta_i \quad (1)$$

where x_i and η_i are respectively the mole-fraction and viscosity of the pure i -th component. Kendall and Munroe¹³ presented a logarithmic equation for the calculation of viscosity which for a multi-component system takes the form,

$$\ln \eta = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \ln \eta_i \quad (2)$$

The additive viscosity relation based on Arrhenius model¹⁴ and Eyring's model¹⁵ for the viscosity of pure liquids, can be extended to ternary liquid mixture as,

$$\ln \eta V = x_1 \ln \eta V_1 + x_2 \ln \eta V_2 + x_3 \ln \eta V_3 \quad (3)$$

where V_i is the molar volume of the pure i -th component.

Frenkel¹⁶ with the help of Eyring's model developed the logarithmic relation for nonideal binary liquid mixtures which has been extended for ternary liquid system,

$$\begin{aligned} \eta = & x_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + x_2^2 \ln \eta_2 + x_3^2 \ln \eta_3 + \\ & 2(x_1 x_2 \ln \eta_{12} + x_2 x_3 \ln \eta_{23} + x_3 x_1 \ln \eta_{31}) \\ & + 3x_1 x_2 x_3 \ln \eta_{123} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Very recently¹⁰, Flory's statistical theory has been successfully used to study the viscous behaviour of multicomponent liquid systems. The final viscosity equation for ternary mixtures obtained on the basis of this theory may be written as

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_3 \ln \eta_3$$

TABLE 1—COEFFICIENT OF THERMAL EXPANSION (α), COMPRESSIBILITY (β) AND DENSITY (ρ) OF THE PURE COMPONENTS AT VARYING TEMPERATURES

Sl. no.	Temp. K	$10^4 \times \alpha_1$ K ⁻¹	$10^4 \times \alpha_2$ K ⁻¹	$10^4 \times \alpha_3$ K ⁻¹	$10^6 \times \beta_{T_1}$ kPa ⁻¹	$10^6 \times \beta_{T_2}$ kPa ⁻¹	$10^6 \times \beta_{T_3}$ kPa ⁻¹	ρ_1 g ml ⁻¹	ρ_2 g ml ⁻¹	ρ_3 g ml ⁻¹
Set I ($x_1 = 0.4396, x_2 = 0.4158$)										
1.	489	3.722	3.629	4.008	0.103	0.100	0.098	1.958 5	1.861 2	1.970 4
2.	599	3.881	3.779	4.193	0.114	0.106	0.102	1.878 3	1.779 1	1.8917
3.	622	3.916	3.813	4.234	0.116	0.107	0.142	1.861 6	1.762 0	1.875 3
4.	655	3.967	3.861	4.294	0.119	0.109	0.104	1.837 5	1.737 4	1.851 7
5.	716	4.156	3.954	4.409	0.126	0.112	0.107	1.793 0	1.691 9	1.808 1
6.	753	4.138	4.013	4.482	0.131	0.114	0.108	1.766 1	1.664 3	1.781 6
Set II ($x_1 = 0.4421, x_2 = 0.4885$)										
1.	457	3.678	3.587	3.957	0.101	0.097	0.098	1.981 8	1.885 1	1.993 2
2.	459	3.681	3.589	3.960	0.101	0.097	0.099	1.980 4	1.883 6	1.991 8
3.	481	3.711	3.618	3.995	0.103	0.090	0.100	1.964 3	1.868 0	1.976 1
4.	513	3.756	3.661	4.047	0.105	0.099	0.101	1.941 0	1.843 3	1.953 2
5.	575	3.845	3.746	4.151	0.111	0.101	0.104	1.895 8	1.797 0	1.908 9
6.	591	3.869	3.768	4.179	0.113	0.101	0.105	1.884 2	1.785 1	1.897 4
7.	646	3.953	3.848	4.277	0.118	0.104	0.108	1.844 1	1.744 1	1.858 1
8.	673	3.996	3.888	4.337	0.121	0.105	0.109	1.824 4	1.723 9	1.838 8
9.	698	4.036	3.926	4.375	0.124	0.106	0.111	1.806 2	1.705 3	1.820 9
10.	785	4.183	4.065	4.458	0.135	0.109	0.116	1.742 7	1.640 4	1.758 7
11.	789	4.190	4.072	4.556	0.135	0.109	0.117	1.739 8	1.637 4	1.755 8
12.	792	4.195	4.077	4.562	0.136	0.110	0.117	1.737 6	1.635 2	1.723 7

TABLE 2—COMPARISON BETWEEN THEORETICAL AND OBSERVED VALUES OF TERNARY LIQUID MELT (KNO₃ + NaNO₂ + NaNO₃) AT VARYING TEMPERATURES

Sl. no.	Temp. K	η_{expt} cp	η_{Bing} cp	η_{KM} cp	η_{add} cp	η_{Frenk} cp	η_{Flory} cp	$\Delta\%$				
								Bing	KM	add	Frenk	Flory
Set I ($x_1 = 0.4396, x_2 = 0.4158$)												
1.	489	5.275	4.716	4.723	4.664	5.342	4.840	10.59	10.46	11.58	-1.27	8.25
2.	599	2.505	2.700	2.690	2.658	2.915	2.734	-7.78	-7.38	-6.12	-16.37	-9.14
3.	622	2.108	2.392	2.379	2.351	2.621	2.419	-9.72	-9.13	-7.84	-20.23	-10.96
4.	655	1.915	2.021	2.003	1.979	2.128	2.042	-5.53	-4.59	-3.34	-11.12	-6.63
5.	716	1.585	1.496	1.479	1.462	1.538	1.521	5.62	6.69	7.76	2.92	4.40
6.	753	1.442	1.263	1.239	1.225	1.277	1.284	12.41	14.08	15.05	11.44	10.96
Mean percentage deviation								8.608	8.722	8.615	10.453	8.39
Set II ($x_1 = 0.4421, x_2 = 0.4885$)												
1.	457	6.205	6.215	6.215	6.152	6.746	7.231	-0.16	-0.16	0.85	-8.70	16.50
2.	459	6.372	6.010	6.010	5.949	6.514	6.981	0.06	0.06	0.07	-2.20	-9.50
3.	481	4.755	4.924	4.923	4.873	5.289	5.676	-3.60	-3.50	-2.50	-11.20	-19.40
4.	513	3.911	4.109	4.107	4.067	4.377	4.681	-5.10	-5.01	-3.99	-11.90	-19.70
5.	575	2.569	3.024	3.018	2.990	3.176	3.369	-17.71	-17.48	-16.38	-23.62	-31.10
6.	591	2.217	2.713	2.784	2.759	2.999	3.091	-25.98	-25.57	24.45	-35.27	-39.41
7.	646	1.868	2.092	2.073	2.055	2.154	2.260	-11.99	-10.97	-10.01	-15.31	-20.98
8.	673	1.591	1.803	1.783	1.768	1.843	1.924	-13.32	-12.06	-11.12	-15.84	-20.93
9.	698	1.408	1.568	1.548	1.535	1.592	1.656	-11.36	-9.94	-9.02	-13.07	-17.61
10.	785	1.218	1.121	1.100	1.091	1.118	1.189	7.96	9.69	10.42	8.21	2.38
11.	789	1.231	1.106	1.078	1.077	1.103	1.110	10.15	12.40	12.51	10.39	9.82
12.	792	1.143	1.086	1.067	1.059	1.083	1.151	4.99	6.65	7.35	5.25	-0.01
Mean percentage deviation								9.365	9.457	9.056	13.413	17.278

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \left[x_1 P_1^* V_1^* \left\{ \frac{1}{\tilde{V}_1} - \frac{1}{\tilde{V}} \right\} + 3\tilde{T}_1 \ln \left\{ \frac{\tilde{V}_1^{1/3} - 1}{\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1} \right\} \right. \\
& + x_2 P_2^* V_2^* \left\{ \frac{1}{\tilde{V}_2} - \frac{1}{\tilde{V}} \right\} + 3\tilde{T}_2 \ln \left\{ \frac{\tilde{V}_2^{1/3} - 1}{\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1} \right\} \\
& + x_3 P_3^* V_3^* \left\{ \frac{1}{\tilde{V}_3} - \frac{1}{\tilde{V}} \right\} + 3\tilde{T}_3 \ln \left\{ \frac{\tilde{V}_3^{1/3} - 1}{\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1} \right\} \\
& \left. + \frac{x_1 V_1^* \theta_2 x_{12}}{\tilde{V}_1} + \frac{x_2 V_2^* \theta_3 x_{23}}{\tilde{V}_2} + \frac{x_3 V_3^* \theta_1 x_{31}}{\tilde{V}_3} \right] / RT \\
& + \frac{1}{(\tilde{V}-1)} - \frac{x_1}{(\tilde{V}_1-1)} - \frac{x_2}{(\tilde{V}_2-1)} - \frac{x_3}{(\tilde{V}_3-1)} \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

where all the symbols have their significant

Results and Discussion

Viscosities are computed for the KNO_3 - NaNO_2 - NaNO_3 ternary liquid melt at two compositions in a set of six and twelve temperatures. The experimental data were taken from the work of Gaune³. To study the effect of composition and temperature on the viscous behaviour of the molten mixture, the

Bingham relation, the Kendall-Munroe relation, the additive relation, the Frenkel relation and the Flory's statistical approach were used. The values of viscosities and molar volume of the pure components were taken from the literature¹⁷ for the temperature range in which the values were available, and the values at the other temperatures were determined by graphical interpolation, all of which are recorded in Table 1. Viscosity shows inverse relation with temperature as is evident from the experimental findings and the theoretical results obtained by using the various relations.

Since at composition I, the third component NaNO_3 is in considerable amount ($x_3 = 0.1446$) as compared to the composition II ($x_3 = 0.0694$), the results obtained for composition I are better as compared to those at composition II (Table 2). This is in consistence with the findings that addition of the third component in multicomponent system weakens the interaction¹⁸. More deviation as observed by applying the Flory's statistical theory, is also due to the fact that this approach is dependent on the values of the coefficient of thermal expansion (α). At different temperatures their values were

TABLE 3—EXCESS VISCOSITY AND INTERACTION PARAMETERS OF SYSTEM ($\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$) AT VARYING TEMPERATURES

Sl. no.	Temp. K	η_{expt} cp	η_{expt}^E	$\eta_{\text{theo-1}}^E$	$\eta_{\text{theo-2}}^E$	ϵ	$10^3 \alpha \Delta F_m$ J mol ⁻¹	$10^3 W_{\text{vis}}$ J mol ⁻¹
Set I ($x_1 = 0.4396$, $x_2 = 0.4158$)								
1.	489	5.275	0.559	0.007	0.124	0.746 4	14.790 0	2.111 0
2.	599	2.505	-0.195	-0.010	0.034	-0.307 1	21.786 1	-1.332 9
3.	622	2.180	-0.212	-0.013	0.027	-0.376 5	23.187 0	-1.746 9
4.	655	1.915	-0.106	-0.018	0.021	-0.193 7	24.866 3	-0.849 7
5.	716	1.585	0.089	-0.017	0.025	0.298 4	24.353 6	1.987 3
6.	753	1.442	0.179	-0.024	-0.021	0.654 0	25.647 1	4.308 1
Set II ($x_1 = 0.4421$, $x_2 = 0.4885$)								
1.	457	6.205	-0.010	0.0	1.015	-0.006 9	6.884 1	0.140 0
2.	459	6.372	0.362	0.0	0.97	0.252 1	6.959 9	1.129 0
3.	481	4.755	-0.169	-0.001	0.752	-0.149 7	7.514 6	-0.426 1
4.	513	3.911	-0.198	-0.002	0.572	-0.210 8	8.409 7	-0.719 2
5.	575	2.569	-0.455	-0.006	0.345	-0.694 3	10.377 4	-3.126 7
6.	591	2.217	-0.576	-0.009	0.298	-0.981 6	10.994 2	-4.627 5
7.	646	1.868	-0.224	-0.019	0.168	-0.448 8	13.544 6	-2.207 0
8.	673	1.591	-0.212	-0.020	0.121	-0.491 1	15.114 4	-2.540 7
9.	698	1.408	-0.160	-0.020	0.088	-0.408 6	16.713 9	-2.161 4
10.	785	1.218	0.097	0.021	0.068	0.439 2	18.288 9	3.081 5
11.	789	1.231	0.125	0.028	0.004	0.572 1	36.876 1	3.967 3
12.	792	1.143	0.057	-0.019	0.065	0.296 6	18.539 6	2.167 9

graphically calculated using the extrapolated density values. Since α is very sensitive to even small temperature variation, hence, to some extent the deviation may also be due to the uncertainty of the extrapolated values of the coefficient of thermal expansion.

Table 3 contains the values of the various interaction parameters. These parameters explain the nature and extent of molecular interactions involved using the concept of the Flory's theory⁵ considering two-body interactions only and the concept of the Gunberg-Nissan¹⁹ in terms of the quantity ϵ where all possible interactions are being considered. The values of the excess free energy of mixing and the interaction energy (W_{vis}) are also recorded in Table 3.

The excess viscosity (η^E) can be evaluated using the relations,

$$\eta_{\text{expt}}^E = \eta_{\text{expt}} - \eta_{\text{ideal}} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \eta_{\text{theo}}^E = \eta_{\text{theo}} - \eta_{\text{ideal}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where, } \eta_{\text{ideal}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i \eta_i \quad (8)$$

Here, the magnitude of η_{expt}^E shows the actual deviation of the system from the ideal behaviour. Its very small magnitude for both the compositions signifies the additive behaviour of viscous properties of the components. $\eta_{\text{theo-1}}^E$ is the excess viscosity calculated from the Flory's theory and $\eta_{\text{theo-2}}^E$ is that calculated from the Kendall-Munroe relation. A close perusal of Table 3 shows a larger variation in case of the Flory's theory because the theory considers only two-body interactions, whereas the possibility of three- and four-body interactions can not be ruled out. But owing to the smaller size of the ions involved these can be neglected.

The Gunberg-Nissan equation enables evaluation of the non-ideal parameter, ϵ ,

$$\ln \eta = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i \ln \eta_i + \epsilon (x_1 x_2 + x_2 x_3 + x_3 x_1 + x_1 x_2 x_3) \quad (9)$$

where ϵ is a measure of non-ideality. From its value recorded (Table 3) it seems that the interactions between ions are weakened by the addition of the third component. The small magnitude of these values at both the composition shows the weakness of interactions, but these interactions tend to increase at very low and high temperatures which is indicated by the small positive values of ϵ .

The values of the excess free energy of mixing ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) and the interaction energy (W_{vis}) can be evaluated using the equations,

$$\alpha\Delta F_m = -RT (\ln \eta_{\text{theo}} - \ln \eta_{\text{ideal}}) \quad (10)$$

$$W_{\text{vis}} = \frac{RT}{\epsilon} \ln \left[\frac{V}{x_1 x_2 x_3} \frac{V_1 V_2 V_3}{V} \right] + \epsilon RT \quad (11)$$

Negative W_{vis} and positive values of excess free energy of mixing indicate weakness of interactions. Weak interactions at both the compositions are confirmed by the positive values of $\alpha\Delta F_m$. That these interactions tend to strengthen at low (< 500 K) and high (>700 K) temperatures, is confirmed by the small positive values of W_{vis} at these temperatures. This behaviour is probably due to the fact that though at lower temperatures ionic interactions exist, at very high temperatures interionic and interelectronic interactions also have their existence.

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